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The reception of Modern Architecture

This paper deals with the reception theory, which will be the subject for the Seventh DOCOMOMO Conference to be held in Paris in September 2002.

On the proposal of the French working party, DOCOMOMO International has decided that the next issue of the international Conference, which will take place in Paris, will be devoted to the reception of the works of the Modern Movement. The title of the Conference is "The Modern Movement, meaning and controversies. The reception and interpretations of the Modern Movement: Massmedia, myth and social value"¹. I believe that this issue will be welcomed by those who share an ambitious vision of the legacy of Modern Architecture and also assume the complexity of this heritage, which is intimately intertwined with the values that have been raised and conveyed by Modern Architecture.

Hans Robert Jauss was the founder of the reception theory. In his essays, he is proposing an ambitious method. On the whole, the "reception" consists in analysing the circumstances, the environment in which a particular work of art is being created, produced, criticized, and judged. Jauss' research was primarily devoted to literature, but his writings on the reception theory address more widely the field of art. When published in the seventies, this theory was carrying the methods in Art History away from the current opposition between methodologies still more or less inspired by the idealist philosophy on one hand, versus methodologies influenced by the various materialist theories concerning the mechanical relationship between art and society that had been in vogue especially since the early sixties. Some traits of the analysis of the reception explain why and how it can be productive in the field of "modern" architectural studies. First, after a particular architectural project is being built, there exists a judgement of this building.

Judgement is a key concept in Jauss' approach, which he borrows directly from Emmanuel Kant (Kant, 1790). A first form of judgement is provided by the writings of the critics. Very often irrelevant of the reception by the critics, or even in contradiction with them, there also exists other forms of judgement of the buildings: the number of people visiting the buildings and monuments that are open to the public is one of the forms of the judgement. The way people live in these buildings, the way they are being taken care of, or restored, the preservation of them takes also part of the so-called "reception". All these meanings of the reception have to do with the life cycle of a particular building once it is already built. Gérard Monnier and Jacques Repiquet will cover those forms of reception in their own communications.

*Also very importantly, the reception embraces the circumstances from which a particular building takes its sources; the inspirations, the sources of influence, the economic and social conditions also belong to a less well-spread aspect of the analysis of the reception. The issues involved are intimately related to the values that were raised by and were awarded to Modern Architecture in a particular context, and still are. This question is of general interest for all the people concerned with building, because Modern Architecture has raised a renewal of the formal language of architecture, an ambitious, social oriented, generous system of values, which is probably without precedent; those meanings and values were brought during a period which, on the whole, bore extreme contrasts between certain periods of Golden Age and others of mere catastrophes, as the historian Eric Hobsbawm has pointed in his book *The Age of Extremes* (Hobsbawm, 1994). The destiny of the villa of the Tugendhat family, created by Ludwig Mies van der Rohe in Brno (1928-1930), bears reflection upon those contrasts. They resulted into a deep transformation of the meaning and use of the villa: after serving only eight years as a home for the Tugendhat, the villa was confiscated by the Gestapo in 1940, then inhabited by several German people living in Brno; it was severely damaged at the end of the war. After the war, it was owned by the national management service and first served from 1945 until 1950 as a ballet school. It hosted the rehabilitation Department of the local Children Hospital in the sixties. Interest in the villa as cultural heritage began in the early sixties as a result of the action of figures of the former Brno Movement, amongst them František Kalivoda. It culminated only in the eighties with the first steps taken for the restoration of the villa, and in 1995 when the building was granted the "National Cultural Monument" status (Kudelka and Teplý, 2001: pp.18-21).*

International, national and local networks or influences play an important role in Modern Architecture. Those networks bear certain specificities during the period of emergence, development and maturation of the Modern Movement. Migration is one of those factors. Eliel Saarinen's emigration to the United States in 1923 bears major developments in three fields: the architectural debate on the skyscraper type and on city planning theories, and the education of American architects and designers (Chevallier, in Barré-Despont, 1996: pp.139-140; pp.526-527). Saarinen is a case of his own. He emigrated for economic reasons. From 1924 until 1934 another vague of migrations had an ideological founding. German architects, amongst whom Oswald Schneideratus, Eric Mendelsohn and Ernst May accepted works in the USSR; some of them emigrated (Kopp, 1988: pp.253-260). This type of migration, mainly from German origin, also reached Le Corbusier in France, who was chosen at the competition launched for the Centrosoyouz project in Moscow (Cohen, 1992). A major aspect of those human migrations is that they also favoured the migration and reinterpretation of types and models, like in the case of Ernst May's use of modern city planning theories in the USSR. From 1934 on, the third major cause of emigration is well-known. It was the reaction against the nazi regime in Germany and its influences in European countries like Austria, the Czech Republic and Romania. Architects emigrated in the USA, but also in Palestine and in New-Zealand. The second main specificity of the international architectural network is the role played by the Museum of Modern Art. Major traits mark the specificities of this role during the period 1932-1944. First, the MOMA acts as a powerful source of judgement and recognition of European masters; this is a major discriminatory function, which is well illustrated in the recognition of the Finnish designer and architect Alvar Aalto, the only European architect to benefit from an individual exhibition in 1938. At the same token, judgement on European Architecture is directed towards a productive and national impact, because what is expected from this recognition is a renewal of the architectural field in the USA. These traits are present as soon as 1932, as Terence Riley has noted in reference with the famous architectural event "Modern Architecture, International Exhibition" (Riley, 1992), but also very strikingly in Alfred Barr's preface for the catalogue devoted to the Bauhaus in conjunction with the exhibition shown in 1938 at the Museum of Modern Art² (Barr in Bayer, Gropius and al., 1938: pp.5-7). A second important trait of the exhibitions held on European Modern Architecture at the Museum of Modern Art in the thirties is

that the articles, written by American curators, are full of political and social assumptions: for example Catherine Bauer delivers a high critical appraisal in favour of the social policy of the British Labour Party in the catalogue published in conjunction with the exhibition on "Modern Architecture in England" held in 1937 (Russel-Hitchcock and Bauer, 1937: pp.21-22), whereas the catalogue for the Alvar Aalto's exhibition in 1938 is reflecting John McAndrew's and Simon Breines' conceptions on the idea of nation (McAndrew and Breines, 1938; Chevallier, 2000: pp.70-72). The third trait of this period is the fertilization of the American architectural scene and its diffusion through exhibitions; this trait is culminating with the exhibition "Built in the USA 1932-1944", organized by Elizabeth Mock in 1944.

International recognition gained at the Museum of Modern Art during the period 1932-1944 had a powerful impact. Other actors, historians and critics contributed at the time to this international scene of judgement. A local scene was also delivering its judgements sometimes in parallel. The case of Finnish modernism is extremely interesting in this regard; due to the French reception of the Finnish Pavilion at the Paris International Exhibition of 1937 and to the exhibition held at the Museum of Modern Art in 1938, Alvar Aalto was the only Finnish architect to gain international attention, whereas the major architect Erik Bryggman's reputation was confined to the Finnish audience. These judgements also fixed the forms for the debate on modernity and had local long lasting effect on the architectural scene in Finland in the sixties³, until now.

The approach of the reception invites us to revisit the various figures active in the field of architecture. Architectural theory often paves the way for an endogen approach of architecture, where the main or unique actors would be the architects themselves and their networks. The situation is more complex, especially in the field of city-planning. For example, the role of the elected representatives and civil servants, both at national and local level, was often of determining nature at the stage of the definition of the projects, and of the conservation of urban surroundings. That is of course well-known in certain national contexts like in the Dutch one, where the role of certain figures of the social-democrat party, like F.M. Wibaut (1859-1936) in Amsterdam were extremely active in urban and social housing issues from 1914 on. In France, Edouard Herriot, the mayor of Lyon, played a major role in major architectural and urban projects between 1905 and the First World War; his close relationship with the architect Tony Garnier is well-known. But in certain contexts, those actors also played a major role for raising urban issues and promote the diffusion of experiences and competence in this field, sometimes on an interna-

tional scale. The period between 1919 and 1930 in France provides examples of such networks. They take their sources primarily in the necessities of the reconstruction, in the hygienist ideals and in the ambitions of providing housing for the poorest categories of the population. Philanthropic ideals are also at stake in this debate. The French review *La Construction Moderne* reports on the activity of those networks, feeding the architectural debate and echoing the problems faced in Paris: insalubrious housing, development of the car traffic, density problems. In 1919, the review records the action of a philanthropic and social oriented society, called "La Renaissance des Cités". The author of the article, Pierre Bourdeix, is the director of Civil Works in the city of Armentières. The aim of this society is to develop urban schemes that would encourage primarily a vision of "social order" that is particularly needed after the disasters of the First World War (Bourdeix, 1919: pp.34-35). In 1920, the inter-Allied Town Planning Conference is reported in the review (Bourdeix, 1920: pp.153-155). The members of the Conference are town planners coming from different countries, amongst which Great Britain, the United States, Belgium, the Netherlands, Denmark, Sweden and Norway. Geo Ford, an American town-planner, plays an important role in this Conference as the representative of the American Red Cross in France. This Conference is a major tool for the diffusion of the ideals and practices of town planning in France. Another international event takes place in Paris in 1928: the International Congress on Housing and Urban Planning (Congrès international de l' Habitation et de l' Aménagement des villes) (Descamps, 1928 : pp. pp.597-599). The main actors of this Congress are political representatives. Paul Strauss, a senator, and former French Minister of Hygiene, opens the Conference with the French Minister of Labour, Louis Loucheur⁴. M.G. Montagu Harris, a representative of the British Minister of Hygiene, chairs the committee on " Housing for the poorest ", whereas the French Henri Sellier, the mayor of Suresnes, a political figure very active in urban and social issues, delivers the report on those issues. Ernst May, as the director of the architectural office of Frankfurt, is chairing the committee on city-plans methods and legislation. These committees are an excellent opportunity for the mutualisation of experiences, competences and know-how.

The research on conservation or revitalization of urban schemes also addresses various actors involved in the life of the city. The French context of Vénissieux, in the area of Lyon, provides approaches in this regard. It is addressing a major social and political issue in France: the remedies to bring to the social costs of the so-called "Grands En-

sembles". Such "Grands Ensembles" were built in Vénissieux in the sixties as a response to a lack of approximately five hundred apartment buildings resulting from an increasing number of migrant workers (Corbel, 1983: pp. 260-277). Social disturbances appeared in Vénissieux as early as in the seventies. The public strategy developed in the eighties as a response to this problem contrasts with the one developed in the 90's; in the eighties, an ambitious urban competition was held with the aim of proposing multi-dimensional solutions, concerning architecture, the public transportation, the economy, the lack of intellectual and scientific resources. We can observe in such a strategy a strong belief in the myth of the architectural competition as a way to solve the problems of human life, a myth inherited from the glorious years of the Modern Movement. The social response was to take its origin from the architectural field. Since the 90's, the strategy favours a variety of actions at the local level, including the use of the resources of local democracy. Urban memory is seen as a major tool in order to prevent social disturbances: in this context, the idea of Urban Heritage serves primarily a social aim.

The reception theory provides fruitful approaches for a critical appraisal of the Modern Movement, of its various contexts, and of its meaning and legacy.

NOTES

¹ This title was the one adopted by the DOCOMOMO Council in Brasilia when the present paper was delivered. It was changed after the Brasilia Conference during the first working session of the scientific committee. The title of the Conference is now: "The reception of Architecture of the Modern Movement: Image, Usage, Heritage".

² Barr's preface provides an educational program in architecture that is borrowed from his own reception of the principles of the Bauhaus (see Barr in Bayer, Gropius and al., 1938: 6)

³ The reception of "kivikirkko" (the stone church) in Helsinki by Timo and Tuomi Suomalainen, and of the building Dipoli by Reima Pietilä in the sixties illustrates this point, which is borrowed from Roger Connah (Connah, 1998: pp. 43-47). At the time there existed a latent theoretical scission between two models: "organic" practices, which were acceptable from Aalto, as an isolated figure in the Finnish scene, and an uncompromising abstraction, claimed as fidelity to the Modern Movement and defended by Aulis Blomstedt and Arno Ruusuvoori. The Suomalainen's church and Pietilä's Dipoli did not fit in this scene.

⁴ Louis Loucheur was an important political figure; a former industrialist, he was nominated as Minister of Labour of the government Raymond Poincaré in June 1928. In 1928, he prepared a law allowing state loans and subsidies in favour of social housing; this law was adopted by the Parliament in July 1928.

Fig. 1 – Alvar Aalto, building of the Turun Sanomat, Turku (Finland), 1929 (Photograph G. Welin, Museum of Finnish Architecture)

Fig. 2 – Erik Bryggman, villa Warén in Ruissalo (Finland), 1934 (Photograph G. Welin, Museum of Finnish Architecture)

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